

The Role of Swadhar Greh Centers of Karnataka in Protecting Women

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ABSTRACT:

The status of women in India is highly influenced by the patriarchal society. Women in general are the easy victims of domestic violence, discrimination, caste based atrocities in many situations across communities in India. As repercussions to family/ individual /societal conflicts Women are subjected to heinous crimes such as violence, murder, eve teasing, Kidnapping, rape etc. According to National Crime Records Bureau 2020; –A total of 3,71,503 cases of crime against women were registered during 2020. The crime rate recorded per lakh women population is 56.5 in 2020 compared to 62.3 in 2019.

Considering the crime rates against women in India, the Government of India has taken up measures to reduce and prevent atrocities against women through strict judiciary measures. Further by considering the effect of crime on the victim, the central government has taken up remedial and protective measures towards women who are in distress. One such measures include the Swadhar Greh Scheme. This yojana/scheme addresses to those women in distress especially due to marital violence, societal crimes, etc. by providing immediate psychological and social support through short stay shelter homes that includes free medical and judicial support along with rehabilitative measures in order to bring them back to the mainstream society.

KEYWORDS:

Remedial, Rehabilitation, Mainstream, Empowerment, Self-reliance, Domestic violence, Distress.

Introduction:

The Government of India constitutionally protects Women and Children under its various programs. These programs are authorized to the respective state governments for implementation. These programs assure to provide help to women in order to seek justice through remedial and rehabilitative measures. Thus, the Government of India has included several progressive programs for empowering and protecting women and children.

In this background the central Government has setup separate departments that focusses on the aspects of welfare, development, protection, self-reliance, financial independence and security for women. During the early years, the Department of Women and Child Welfare was functioning under the Ministry of Human Resources Development. But in the year 1985, a separate ministry for Women and Child development was established by the central government. Following this the Karnataka State Government established the Department of Women and Child Development in the year 1994. Thus the Department of Women and Child welfare in Karnataka functions by receiving funds from the Central government's Ministry for Women and Child Development which is considered as the mother organization. Thus the state department strives for the welfare and development of women and children in Karnataka.

The Department of Women and Child Development, Karnataka has been implementing several programs for overall development of women. Through various schemes the WCD fosters the empowerment of women in social, economic, educational, political fields. Further this department strives to protect women and bring them to the mainstream society through programs and schemes such as:

1. Beti Bachao, Beti Pado scheme
2. One Stop Centre Scheme
3. Women Helpline
4. Ujjwala Yojana
5. Swadhaar Greh Yojana
6. Mahila Shakti Kendra Yojana
7. Nirbhaya Yojana

Thus, the central and the state governments under the ministry has been currently implementing these schemes for the welfare and protection of women. And among these schemes the ‘Swadhaar Greh Scheme’ has been one of the pioneering schemes in India that has been implemented for the protection of Women.

Swadhaar Greh Yojana

In the year 2016–17 the Central Government started implementation of the ‘Swadhar Greh Yojana’ by merging the Short Stay home Scheme and the Swadhaar scheme.

The Ministry of Women and Child Development is implementing the Swadhar Greh Scheme which targets the women victims of difficult circumstances who are in need of institutional support for rehabilitation so that they could lead their life with dignity. The Scheme envisages providing shelter, food, clothing and health as well as economic and social security for these women. The beneficiaries of this yojana also include widows, women who are deserted and are without any social and economic support, older women up to the age of 55years, women survivors of natural disasters who have been rendered homeless, women prisoners released from jail and are without family, women victims of domestic violence made to leave their homes without any means of subsis-

tence facing litigation .and also Trafficked women/girls rescued or runaway from brothels or other places where they face exploitation and Women affected by HIV/AIDS who do not have any social or economic support. However such women/ girls should first seek assistance under Ujjawala Scheme in areas where it is in operation.

The Swadhar Greh Yojana is a centrally sponsored scheme. The Centre releases funds for this scheme in a shared proportion The Centre provides 60 percent of the funds to the state to run the Swadhar Greh and the state contributes the remaining share of 40 percent. However for the Himalayan and North-eastern states the Centre releases 90 percent of the funds and the states contribute 10 percent of the funds for implementing the scheme. And the centrally governed states receive 100 percent of the funds for this scheme.

Under the Scheme, Swadhar Greh will be set up in every district with capacity of 30 women.

Civil Society Organizations such as NGOs etc. having proven track record of working in the fields of women's welfare/social welfare/ women's education subject to the condition are eligible to implement this scheme. And that such organization should be registered under the Indian Societies Registration Act, 1860 or any relevant State Act. These Civil Society organization should be at least 3 years old and should be financial stable for establishing the required provisions of Swadhar greh scheme such as food, shelter, clothing, medical care, pocket expense for residents and children.

The benefit of the component could be availed by women above 18 years of age. Women affected by domestic violence could stay up to one year. For other categories of women, the maximum period of stay could be up to 3 years. The older women above the 55 years of age may be accommodated for maximum period of 5 years after which they will have to shift to old age homes or simi-

lar institutions.

According to the 2020–21 Annual report that was released by the Ministry of Women and Child Development (WCD), there are a total of 362 Swadhar Greh Centers functioning in India. There are 7719 beneficiaries in the Swadhar Greh across India. The Indian government has set aside Rupees Fifty Crores in its 2020–21 central budget for the purpose of expenditure towards Swadhar Greh.

According to the 2020–21 Annual report that was released by the Ministry of Women and Child Development (WCD), there are a total of 52 Swadhar Greh Centres functioning in Karnataka State. There are 1378 beneficiaries in the Swadhar Greh across Karnataka. The Karnataka Government received Rupees 272.84 Lakhs from the Indian government's 2020–21 central budget for the purpose of expenditure towards Swadhar Greh in Karnataka.

**Swadhar Greh Scheme– State– wise Homes and Beneficiaries
for FY 2020–21 (As on 31.12.2020)**

Sl No	States/UTs	Homes	Beneficiaries
1.	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	1	9
2.	Andhra Pradesh	22	467
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	1	12
4.	Assam	16	232
5.	Bihar	00	00
6.	Chandigarh	01	05
7.	Chhattisgarh	03	55

8.	Delhi	02	38
9.	Gujarat	09	106
10	Himachal Pradesh	01	09
11.	Jammu & Kashmir	03	27
12.	Jharkhand	05	17
13.	Karnataka	52	1378
14.	Kerala	07	165
15.	Madhya Pradesh	16	230
16.	Maharashtra	09	165
17.	Manipur	23	335
18.	Mizoram	11	129
19.	Meghalaya	02	12
20.	Nagaland	02	35
21.	Odisha	55	1669
22.	Punjab	02	34
23.	Puducherry	01	10
24.	Rajasthan	09	167

25.	Sikkim	01	20
26	Tamil Nadu	35	861
27.	Telangana	23	389
28.	Tripura	03	64
29.	Uttar Pradesh	13	295
30.	Uttarakhand	01	00
31.	West Bengal	33	784
	Total	362	7719

Source: Ministry of women and child development government of India annual report 2020–21, page No –142, 143

Swadhar Greh Scheme (Karnataka) District wise Homes and Beneficiaries for FY 2020–21

Sl No	Districts	Centers
1.	Bagalkote	03
2.	Bengaluru (U)	10
3.	Bengaluru (R)	02
4.	Belagaum	03
5.	Bidhar	03
6.	Vijayapura	01

7.	Chamarajnagara	02
8.	Chikkamagaluru	01
9.	Chikkaballapura	01
10.	Chitradurga	01
11.	Dakshina Kannada (Mangaluru)	01
12.	Davangere	02
13.	Dharwada	03
14.	Gadag	01
15.	Kalaburgi	02
16.	Hasana	01
17.	Haveri	02
18.	Kolar	01
19.	Koppala	01
20.	Mandya	04
21.	Raichur	01
22.	Ramanagara	01
23.	Shivamogga	02

24.	Tumakuru	01
25.	Uttara Kannada	01
26.	Yadagiri	01
	Total	52

Source: 2020–21 Annual Report Department of Women and Child Development; Department for the Empowerment of Differently Abled and Senior Citizens; Government of Karnataka

The status of women in India is highly influenced by the patriarchal society. Women in general are the easy victims of domestic violence, discrimination, caste based atrocities in many situations across communities in India. Women are subjected to heinous crimes such as violence, murder, eve teasing, Kidnapping, rape etc. as repercussions to family/ individual /societal conflicts. According to National Crime Records Bureau 2020; –A total of 3,71,503 cases of crime against women were registered during 2020. The crime rate recorded per lakh women population is 56.5 in 2020 compared to 62.3 in 2019.

Figure: Pie Chart representing the percentage of crime against women in India according to NCRB 2020

Considering the crime rates against women in India, the Government of India has taken up measures to reduce and prevent atrocities against women through strict judiciary measures. Further by considering the effect of crime on the victim, the central government has taken up remedial and protective measures towards women who are in distress. One such measures include the Swadhar Greh Scheme. This yojana/scheme addresses to those women in distress especially due to marital violence, societal crimes, etc. by providing immediate psychological and social support through short stay shelter homes that includes free medical and judicial support along with rehabilitative measures in order to bring them back to the mainstream society.

The term ‘Swadhar’ means ‘self-reliance’, Hence the Swadhar Yojana, is an effort to help women victims of crime and who lack social and economic support to become self-reliant, and lead a life with dignity.

The main Objectives of Swadhar Greh Yojana is as follows:

Under the Scheme, Swadhar Greh will be set up in every district with capacity of 30 women with the following objectives:

- » To cater to the primary need of shelter, food, clothing, medical treatment and care of the women in distress and who are without any social and economic support.
- » To enable them to regain their emotional strength that gets hampered due to their encounter with unfortunate circumstances.
- » To provide them with legal aid and guidance to enable them to take steps for their readjustment in family/society.
- » To rehabilitate them economically and emotionally.
- » To act as a support system that understands and meets various

requirements of women in distress.

- » To enable them to start their life afresh with dignity and conviction.

This study envisages the status of Swadhar Greh in Karnataka. Karnataka has been a state that has strived to reduce at crime rates against women. And thus the scenario of crime against women in Karnataka has been provided in the below Table.

**Violent Crimes against women in India and Karnataka
(NCRB 2020)**

India		Karnataka
Kind of crime	2020	2020
Total Crime Against Women	371503	12680
Crime rate Against Women (per lakh population)	78.6	84.7
Different types of Crime Against Women		
Cyber Crimes/information Technology Act (Women Centric Crimes only) (total)	2334	143
Murder with Rape/Gang Rape	219	7
Human Trafficking	646	12
Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961	10366	1511
Rape + POCOS (Total Rape)	28046+46123=74169	504+2092=2596
Kidnapping & Abduction of Women (Total)	62300	923

Cruelty by Husband or his relatives	111549	2055
Attempt to Commit Rape	3741	11
Dowry Deaths	6966	176
Abetment to Suicide of Women	5040	257
Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act 1956 (Total)	868	159
Insult to the Modesty of Women (Total)	7065	70
Acid Attack	105	5
Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986	12	1
Miscarriage	239	2

With 52 Swadhar Centres in Karnataka, there has been an intense effort by government of Karnataka to provide relief to the women in difficult circumstances. However, there is a need to understand the impact of Swadhar Greh on the women who have received its benefits.

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Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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